

Voltammetric reduction behaviour of *N*-(benzylidene)-2-aminopyridine

T. V. D. Prasad Rao, G. Veerabhadram* and K. S. Sastry

Department of Chemistry, Nizam College, Osmania University, Hyderabad-500 001, India

Manuscript received 24 May 2000, revised 15 December 2000, accepted 2 February 2001

N-(Benzylidene)-2-aminopyridine has been found to be reduced voltammetrically with uptake of four electrons in acidic media and two electrons in basic media based on characterization of products obtained from controlled potential electrolysis. The protonation of >CH=N- group present in the compound precedes the electronation in reduction process. The reduction process is found to be diffusion-controlled and irreversible from voltammetric techniques. The kinetic parameters such as heterogeneous forward rate constant ($k_{f,h}^0$) and activation free energy change (ΔG) have been evaluated. A plausible reduction mechanism has been suggested.

There are reports on electrochemical reduction of carbonyl compounds, but only a few on aromatic Schiff bases¹. Schiff bases and their metal complexes are known for their biological importance². The pyridine moiety as a part of pyridine-2-carboxylaldehyde-2-quinolyhydrazone has been used in detection of metal ions³. It also possesses significant antitumor activity⁴. Hence it was thought worthwhile to study voltammetric reduction of *N*-(benzylidene)-2-aminopyridine, a Schiff base, derived from 2-aminopyridine and benzaldehyde in the pH range 2.0–13.0. Kinetic parameters ($k_{f,h}^0$ and ΔG) are evaluated to study diffusion-controlled nature and irreversibility of the reduction process. The products from controlled potential electrolysis (CPE) are characterised with UV, IR and ¹H NMR spectra. Here, results from voltammetric techniques, viz. dc polarography at DME, cyclic voltammetry, differential pulse polarography at GCE, CPE at mercury pool cathode and reduction mechanism of the title compound are reported.

Results and Discussion

DC polarography : *N*-(Benzylidene)-2-aminopyridine gives a single reduction wave (Fig. 1) in BR buffers of pH range 4.72–13.0, but no reduction wave is observed below pH 4.72. This may be due to basic nature and electron-withdrawing effect of amine moiety of the Schiff base. They are expected to increase with the increase in number of heteroatoms in heterocyclic ring⁵. The half-wave potentials ($E_{1/2}$) of *N*-(benzylidene)-2-aminopyridine were found to be dependent on pH and shifted to more negative potentials with increasing in pH, revealing that protons are consumed in reduction process. The plot $-E_{1/2}$ vs pH consists of two linear segments intersecting at pH 8.10. A remarkable change in $E_{1/2}$ values are observed below pH 8.10 and the slope is 0.0675, and above pH 8.10 there is a small change in $E_{1/2}$ values and slope value is significantly small (0.01). Similar behaviour of $-E_{1/2}$ vs pH plots are observed in literature⁶. The nearly constant $E_{1/2}$ values above pH 8.10 may be due to the fact that acidic (protonated) and basic

Fig. 1. DC polarogram of *N*-(benzylidene)-2-aminopyridine at pH 4.72.

(unprotonated) forms of depolariser are electroactive at the electrode surface, but in pH range where the equilibrium between basic and acidic forms tends towards basic form, the half-wave potentials are close to each other⁷. It indicates that the protonation of azomethine group (>CH=N-) present in the Schiff base precedes the electronation in the reduction process,

Table 1. Kinetic parameters of 1mM *N*-(benzylidene)-2-aminopyridine in buffer solutions

pH	i_d µA	$-E_{1/2}$ V	Slope (S_1) = (0.06015/ αn_a)	αn_a	$10^{18} k_{f,h}^0$ cm s ⁻¹	ΔG kcal mol ⁻¹
4.72	4.18	1.186	0.0758	0.791	27.34	28.65
5.63	3.87	1.248	0.0789	0.734	13.82	29.06
7.21	3.49	1.352	0.0847	0.699	6.12	29.55
9.04	2.93	1.421	0.0865	0.676	1.83	30.28
10.49	2.25	1.430	0.0870	0.668	1.73	30.31
11.25	2.12	1.440	0.0875	0.661	1.59	30.36
12.60	1.87	1.457	0.0885	0.653	1.46	30.42

Slope (S_2) = ($\Delta E_{1/2}/\Delta \text{pH}$) = 0.0675.

The irreversibility of reduction process is evident from the slopes of log plots ($-E_{de}$ vs $\log i/i_d - i$), increasing with pH. The number of electrons involved in overall reduction process has been determined by millicoulometry and found to be four in acidic media and two in basic media. The number of protons (p) involved in r.d.s. step has been calculated from the slopes of log plots (S_1) and plot $-E_{1/2}$ vs pH (S_2) and found to be one.

The kinetic parameters, viz. heterogeneous forward rate constant ($k_{f,h}^0$) and activation free energy change (ΔG) were evaluated from dc polarography and are reported⁸ in Table 1. The values of $k_{f,h}^0$ decreases whereas ΔG increases with pH, indicating the increasing tendency of irreversibility.

Cyclic voltammetry and DPP : *N*-(Benzylidene)-2-aminopyridine gives a single cathode peak/wave below pH 10.49, but thereafter two well-defined cathodic peaks/

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammogram of *N*-(benzylidene)-2-aminopyridine at pH 7.21 and at scan rates (a) 100, (b) 200 mV s^{-1} .

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammogram of *N*-(benzylidene)-2-aminopyridine at pH 10.49 and at scan rates (a) 100, (b) 200 mV s^{-1} .

waves are observed both in cyclic voltammetry and differential pulse polarography at GCE (Figs. 2–4). The single peak/wave below pH 10.49 and second peak/wave above

Fig. 4. Differential pulse polarograms of *N*-(benzylidene)-2-aminopyridine at pH values (a) 5.63, (b) 10.49.

Table 2. Cyclic voltammetry and differential pulse polarographic data of 1mM *N*-(benzylidene)-2-aminopyridine at different pH values*

Scan rate mV s^{-1}	5.63		7.21		9.04		10.49	
	$-E_p$ or E_m V	i_p or i_m μA						
Cyclic voltammetry								
20	1.241	2.13	1.336	2.05	1.407	1.69	1.411 (1.013)	1.27 (0.83)
50	1.254	3.02	1.348	2.91	1.419	2.41	1.425 (1.091)	1.83 (1.14)
100	1.262	3.91	1.359	3.53	1.425	2.99	1.437 (1.142)	2.31 (1.35)
150	1.269	4.45	1.365	4.09	1.432	3.56	1.448 (1.184)	2.79 (1.76)
200	1.274	5.11	1.368	4.62	1.436	4.13	1.455 (1.212)	3.16 (2.03)
300	1.282	5.92	1.375	5.41	1.445	4.92	1.464 (1.227)	3.54 (2.47)
DPP	1.257	3.94	1.353	3.45	1.412	2.87	1.429 (1.145)	2.96 (1.97)

*Values in parenthesis corresponds to pre-wave/peak.

pH 10.49 is due to the reduction of azomethine group present in Schiff base. The appearance of pre-peak/wave above pH 10.49 may be due to reduction of carbonyl group present in benzaldehyde, which is formed due to partial hydrolysis of Schiff base in higher alkaline pH values. The C=O group gets reduced at lower reduction potentials than CH=N group as reported⁹. This is further confirmed by the voltammogram of benzaldehyde which gives the peak as that of voltammogram of Schiff base at the same potential taken at the same pH value and scan rate. The appearance of pre-peak/wave above pH 10.49 in cyclic voltammetry and differential pulse polarographic studies at GCE, but not in dc polarography at DME, may be ascribed to the surface effect of glassy carbon electrode on electrolysis. It is supported by the earlier observations¹⁰.

The diffusion-controlled nature of dc polarograms, cyclic voltammograms and dp polarograms is evident from linear plots of i_d vs $h_{1/2}$, i_p vs $v_{1/2}$ and i_m vs $t_{2/3}$, which pass through the origin. The shift in $E_{1/2}$, E_p and E_m values to more negative potentials with increase in concentration of depolariser indicates the irreversibility of electrode process. This is further confirmed by variation of peak potential (E_p) with the increase in pH. The shift in peak potential (E_p) with scan rate (v) in the range of 20–300 mV/s studied (Table 2), clearly rules out the possibility of fast electron transfer, which is a characteristic of reversible reaction.

The differential pulse polarography is used for the quantitative estimation of Schiff base using both calibration and standard addition methods. The electrochemical reduction of Schiff base above pH 10.49 is increasingly difficult due to less availability of protons. The optimum pH range for quantitative detection of Schiff base is 4.72–8.10. In the calibration method, the peak current (i_m) is found to vary linearly with concentration of the electroactive species in the range 2.5×10^{-5} to 1.0×10^{-3} M.

Controlled potential electrolysis: Controlled potential electrolysis of *N*-(benzylidene)-2-aminopyridine has been carried out in buffer solutions of pH values 6.86 and 9.18 at -1.34 V and -1.45 V vs SCE, respectively. The reduction products did not show λ_{\max} above 300 nm after completion of electrolysis, indicating the absence of azomethine group (CH=N). The electrolysed products at pH 6.86 were found to be 2-aminopyridine and toluene due to complete reduction of azomethine group present in Schiff base with uptake of four electrons. The comparison of TLC of electrolysed products with the corresponding 2-aminopyridine shows the presence of 2-aminopyridine. Further, the dye test and 2,3,5,6-tetrachlorobenzoquinone test also reveal the presence of 2-aminopyridine. The isolated amino product from electrolysed products, in acidic media, is confirmed as 2-aminopyridine: ν_{\max} (KBr) 3443 (N–H in primary aromatic amines), 3026 (=C–H aromatic), 1617 (C=C aromatic) and 1274 cm^{-1} (C–N primary aromatic amines);

$^1\text{H NMR}$ δ 8.41 (1H, d, ArH), 7.82 (1H, d, ArH), 7.51 (2H, q, ArH) and 5.74 (2H, s, NH_2).

A comparison of TLC of electrolysed products at pH 9.18 with 2-aminopyridine reveals the absence of primary amine and it is further confirmed by negative response of dye test and 2,3,5,6-tetrachlorobenzoquinone test for primary amines. The electrolysed product in basic conditions was found to be *N*-(benzyl)-2-aminopyridine due to partial reduction of azomethine group present in Schiff base with uptake of two electrons. The isolated product was further confirmed by spectral data: ν_{\max} (KBr) 3356 (N–H), 3034 (=CH aromatic), 1609 (C=N aromatic), 1510 (C=C aromatic), 1317 cm^{-1} (C–N sec. amines); $^1\text{H NMR}$ δ 8.49 (1H, d, py-H), 7.98 (1H, q, py-H), 7.73 (1H, q, py-H), 7.25–7.51 (5H, m, ArH), 7.16 (1H, d, py-H), 4.78 (2H, s, CH_2), 3.78 (N–H hump).

Reduction mechanism: On the basis of the results obtained from all the voltammetric studies, the reduction mechanisms suggested are presented in Schemes 1–3. In acidic media, after protonation (one proton) of azomethine

group present in *N*-(benzylidene)-2-aminopyridine, it consumes two electrons and one proton in a slow step giving *N*-(benzyl)-2-aminopyridine. In a subsequent fast step, it fur-

ther consumes two electrons and two protons (overall consumption of $4e$ and 4H^+) giving toluene and 2-aminopyridine as final products (Scheme 1). In basic media (dc

polarography and CPE) after protonation of >CH=N- group, it consume two electrons and one proton (overall consumption of 2e, 2H⁺) giving *N*-(benzyl)-2-aminopyridine as the final product (Scheme 2). In higher alkaline conditions (cyclic voltammetry and differential pulse polarography at GCE), *N*-(benzylidene)-2-aminopyridine is prone to partial hydrolysis giving benzaldehyde and 2-aminopyridine. The Schiff base undergoes usual (2e, 2H⁺) reduction which gives *N*-(benzyl)-2-aminopyridine as one of the final products (Scheme 3).

Experimental

N-(Benzylidene)-2-aminopyridine was prepared from 2-aminopyridine (Sigma) and benzaldehyde (Sisco) and crystallised in ethanol as described earlier¹¹; its purity was found to be 98–99%. Stock solution of Schiff base (1.0 × 10⁻² M) was prepared in double-distilled methanol. The voltammetric experiments were carried out after deaerating experimental solutions by passing pure nitrogen gas for about 20 min at 303 ± 0.5 K. Triton X-100 (5 × 10⁻⁴%) was used to suppress the polarographic maxima. The polarograms were recorded with a Thoshniwal CL02 polarograph in conjunction with polyflex galvanometer (PL50). The dropping mercury electrode having characteristics of $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.39$ mg, was used as a working electrode and SCE as reference electrode. The cyclic voltammetry and differential pulse polarography experiments were carried out with computer-controlled electroanalysed system CS-1090/CS-1087 (Cypress systems). The system consisted of three micro-electrode assembly in which the glassy carbon electrode (0.5 mm dia) served as working electrode, silver electrode (0.4 mm dia) as reference electrode and platinum electrode (0.5 mm dia) as counter electrode. The CPE was carried out with a potentiostan POS73 (Wenking). The CPE cell consisted of a large surface area (80 cm²) of mercury pool acting as a cathode, platinum foil (4 cm²) as counter electrode (anode) and saturated calomel electrode as reference electrode.

Electronic spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu 1601 PC spectrophotometer, IR spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 1605 spectrophotometer and ¹H NMR spectra on a Varian Gemini spectrometer (200 MHz) using solutions prepared in TMS (tetramethylsilane).

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (T.V.D.P.R.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for providing financial assistance.

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